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Preferred competences by the labour market in the opinion of higher education students

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ABSTRACT

A large-scale development of science and technology began in the twentieth century, which has further intensified in the 21st century, reinforcing the role of innovation and technological development both at the individual and organizational level. In the 21st century, not only the ability to develop is a requirement but technological advancement in different areas simultaneously creates competition and the need for co-operation between various actors. Creativity, complexity and innovation can result in novel methods, innovative or different ways of thinking, but at the same time, players in different industries are now forced to cooperate in certain areas of development as it is in their well-recognised state-of-the-art high-tech solution quickly and cost-effectively.

We were curious to find out what the Hungarian university students thought about what competencies they needed as career starters and what competencies they wanted to develop. We wanted to assess the proportion of students' expectations in the labour market. We started a research at the Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME) Faculty of Economic and Social Sciences (GTK) and we received students' answers from 21 universities out of 28 state universities in Hungary. The goal was to get the views of students in as many higher education institutions as possible. The online questionnaire was popularized at conferences, professional events and in the social media. University professors and students

shared the questionnaire with potential respondents. The response was anonymous and voluntary, in this way, random sampling was performed.

Our hypothesis was that students do not know what the labour market expects of them, and therefore they don't develop their skills in the most appropriate direction, either in their choice of elective subjects or in their choice of tasks when fulfilling the subject requirements.

As a control question, we asked the students to answer whether the institution of higher education they were attending could meet their prior expectations and whether they trust that their schools would prepare them to face the challenges of the labour market.

1. THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVES

Nowadays higher education faces a big issue: universities have to train future employees to meet the expectations of the labour market in a rapidly changing technical and economic environment. The client of higher education is the labour market. Universities must pass on the knowledge of the labour market to students and develop competencies that meet expectations. Universities are in direct contact with employers, there is an ongoing cooperation and dialogue between the parties. Employers invest time, energy and money in teaching their prospective employees. At the same time, employers are confronted during the integration process of young graduates with the fact that fresh graduates have little usable knowledge compared to their expectations. This leads to the customers' dissatisfaction as well as the decrease of the entrants' confidence. It seems that the three actors in the education process - employers, universities and students - need more effective and efficient communication and cooperation. Universities need to understand even better what knowledge and skills they are expected to provide to future employees. The students should be aware of what they learn and how and why this knowledge will be useful to them in their work. This knowledge can help the students to engage in committed and motivated learning, in the conscious acquisition of knowledge. Students do not learn in the hope of passing an exam successfully but in order to be successful in the future. The employer should be aware of what can be taught at universities and what newcomers need to master challenges in the world of work. Information can be the link among the three actors in the training process that would result in the participants' knowing exactly what they do, teach and learn. Information functioning as a bridge is not just about today's expectations, but also about the development of employees how to face future changes. At the same time the role and the immense importance cannot be emphasized enough for employers "Skills and jobs remain in focus and the importance of exposure to the workplace and career guidance: internships, mentoring and site visits." (A. Kálmán 2017)¹

¹ Anikó Kálmán: Lifelong Peer Learning – New Environments and Scenarios to Build Responsive Systems for Societies - IN REPORTS, APPLIED RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT · VOCATIONAL EDUCATION — 12 Apr, 2017

As it was published by OECD in 2002 successful learning, was likely to mean that the learner has a high degree of self-confidence and self-esteem, is highly motivated to learn and its learning environment is "a great challenge" and "low threat". Based on the experiences, the OECD study emphasizes motivation, self-confidence and success as key factors for success in education. ² Higher education must support the students' self-confidence and self-esteem in a way that the learning environment is at the same time a great challenge and low threat. The learning environment should inspire students to learn while providing the security that learners are able to acquire adequacy to the labour market. Students will trust the institution of higher education if they are confident that as a result of their studies they are sure to become a useful and sought-after labour force in the labour market. Students will trust the educational institution if they experience the essential characteristics of reliability, such as integrity, competence and benevolence.³ (Mayer 1995). These features include integrity as keeping the promise, competence, as knowledge, and skills that enable a student to act effectively in a job or situation, benevolence that involves a supportive learning environment. In a supportive learning environment, the student's self-confidence and self-esteem is strengthened as a resource for learning new knowledge.

We started a survey in February 2019 at the Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME) Faculty of Economic and Social Sciences (GTK) and we received students' answers from several universities in Hungary. Responding students had completed at least 1 semester in their higher education studies and had not yet graduated, all of them were active in higher education. The valid responses of 177 respondents to the online questionnaire were evaluated. We were curious to know which students among the 21 different higher education institutions considered labour market competencies important in their profession. These 21 universities are 75% of the 28 state universities in Hungary that are not church or private institutions⁴. The responses were compared to labour market expectations.

2. METHODOLOGY

Our first hypothesis was that students do not know what the labour market expects of them, and therefore they don't develop their skills in the most appropriate direction, either in their choice of elective subjects or in their choice of tasks that can be chosen when fulfilling the subject requirements. In the online survey, the respondents had to select the 5 most important ones according to their perception of the competencies preferred by the labour market. We examined which labour market competencies were considered to be the most important by the students and whether the preferences of the university students coincided with the preferences of their

² Understanding the Brain: Towards a New Learning Science OECD (2002)

³ Roger C. Mayer, James H. Davis, F. David Schoorman: An Integrative Model of Organizational Trust (1995)

⁴ Address Book of Higher Education Institutions, effective from February 15, 2019 Retrieved 28.04.2019 from <http://www.mrk.hu/tagjaink/>

prospective employers. In the following, we examined whether students were given feedback on their skills and trust in their higher education institution, in addition to their grades, in order to prepare them for the labour market expectations. We were looking for a significant relationship between feedback on skills and trust in the institution. Our second hypothesis was that if the student was studying in a supportive environment, one of the manifestations of which was to receive feedback on his / her existing ability, it not only had a positive effect on successful learning, but the student also trusted in the educational institution more. The correlation analysis was performed by SPSS analysis.

3. ANALYSIS OF RESPONSES

The online questionnaire on the question What skills and competencies are most needed in your home country for a graduate in your profession? listed in addition to the 13 competencies expected by Hungarian employers, further 8 competencies that have been defined by non-Hungarian organizations (UK, USA, EU, UNESCO). The 21 competencies listed are thus those defined by Hungarian and international employers. The respondents had to choose the 5 competencies which they judged the most important in their own profession.

As the Figure 1 shows students preferred 8 competencies out of 21 competences preferred by the labour market. The competence that students considered the 5 most important were communication skill, problem recognition, solving skill, self-determination and cooperation skill. Respondents were less favouring important competencies such as proactivity and accountability as competencies of a starter employee – 1.98% and 0.89% of the marked competencies were marked as the most important.

Figure 1
The most important competencies of a career starter in Hungary, according to the opinion of the respondent university students

The next question examined was, *Besides my grades, have I ever received oral or written feedback (even informally) on my existing skills from my teachers?* 59.9% of respondents answered yes to the question but 40,1% answered no. Based on the responses, 2 out of 5 students did not receive feedback on their abilities during their studies. Mayer, previously referred to, says that students will trust the educational institution if they experience the essential characteristics of reliability, such as integrity, competence and benevolence. One of the manifestations of benevolence is attention and feedback, which, if experienced by the student, not only increases confidence in the institution, but the feedback received may be inspiring in his or her development.

Besides my grades, have I ever received oral or written feedback (even informally) on my existing skills from my teachers?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid No	71	40,1	40,1	40,1
Yes	106	59,9	59,9	100,0
Total	177	100,0	100,0	

Figure 2
Received feedback about existing skills - frequency table

The last examined question in the survey was *Do you trust that the educational institution where you are studying prepares you to work in the labour market?* The importance of the question is justified by the fact that the OECD's 2002 study, cited above, states that one of the key factors in learning success is the high motivation of the learner to learn. The motivation of the learner is greatly influenced by the fact if he can trust the future usefulness of the acquired knowledge. 71,8% of the respondents answered yes.

Do you trust that the educational institution where you are studying prepares you to work in the labour market?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid No	50	28,2	28,2	28,2
Yes	127	71,8	71,8	100,0
Total	177	100,0	100,0	

Figure 3
Trust in the educational institution

In the following, during the significance study we examined whether there is a connection between the variables of the second hypothesis. Our second hypothesis was that if the student is studying in a supportive environment, one of the manifestations of which is to receive feedback on his / her existing ability, it not only has a positive effect on successful learning, but he also trusts the educational institution more. As you can see in the cross table, 77% of students who received feedback on their skills from their teachers said they trusted the educational institution to prepare them for the labour market. (*Figure 4*)

Do you trust that the educational institution where you are studying prepares you to work in the labour market?

* Besides my grades, have I ever received oral or written feedback (even informally) on my existing skills from my teachers?

			Besides my grades, have I ever received oral or written feedback (even informally) on my existing skills from my teachers?		Total
			no	yes	
Do you trust that the educational institution where you are studying prepares you to work in the labour market?	no	Count % within Besides my grades, have I ever received oral or written feedback (even informally) on my existing skills from my teachers?	26 36,6%	24 22,6%	50 28,2%
	yes	Count % within Besides my grades, have I ever received oral or written feedback (even informally) on my existing skills from my teachers?	45 63,4%	82 77,4%	127 71,8%
Total		Count % within Besides my grades, have I ever received oral or written feedback (even informally) on my existing skills from my teachers?	71 100,0%	106 100,0%	177 100,0%

Figure 4
Cross tabulation

Using the Chi-Square test, we examined whether there is a significant relationship between the variables. We examined whether there is a link between feedback on skills and trust in the educational institution where the university student pursues higher education. (Figure 5) Since the significance value is $0,043 < p$, - where $p = 0,05$ - we reject the null hypothesis that there is no relationship between the two variables, i.e. there is a relationship between feedback on skills and trust in the institution.

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	4,099 ^a	1	,043		
Continuity Correction ^b	3,438	1	,064		
Likelihood Ratio	4,051	1	,044		
Fisher's Exact Test				,060	,032
Linear-by-Linear Association	4,076	1	,044		
N of Valid Cases	177				

a. 0 cells (0,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 20,06.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Figure 5
Chi-Square Tests

4. CONCLUSION

Examining the responses to the questionnaire survey, it can be stated that students in higher education are aware of the competencies preferred by employers. Although our first hypothesis has not been proven based on the results of the survey, this statement is relevant to learning motivation as a key factor for successful learning (OECD 2002). All of the preferred competences named by employers are considered important, but if they are to be prioritized, there are some that are prioritized more often by responders. The most important competency chosen by students is communication skill.

Based on the responses of students who receive feedback on their skills from their instructors, either formally or informally, it is more likely for the educational institution to prepare for work in the labour market. Our second hypothesis was confirmed, there is a relationship between feedback on skills and trust in the institution but it

cannot be ruled out that other factors also affect students' confidence in the institution. According to Mayers study, students will trust the educational institution if they experience the essential characteristics of reliability, such as integrity, competence and benevolence. (Mayer 1995). Further investigations may be needed to explore the details of the relationship, including additional factors. It may be relevant to examine the impact of the feedback received on the evaluation of the educational institution, with particular regard to the degree of integrity, competence and benevolence.

As a final conclusion, it is worth highlighting the importance of feedback in the light of the preference of communication skills by employers and prospective employees. On the one hand, to receive feedback and, based on your own experience, to give feedback with constructive intention, is a very valuable skill in the world of work. On the other hand as to the trust in the institution, resulting from the study, feedback also contributes to creating a supportive learning environment that directly influences the success of learning. The success of learning is the common goal in which the purpose of the learner, the educational institution, and the employers, as customers, meet.

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